

ANALYSIS OF BENDING STIFFNESS REDUCTION IN LAMINATES DUE TO TRANSVERSE CRACKS AND DELAMINATIONS IN SURFACE LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

In the present work an experimental study of bending stiffness reduction was conducted on carbon/epoxy cross-ply laminates with surface 90° layers with different thicknesses. The initially undamaged laminate samples were statically loaded in 4-point bending by running loading-unloading steps with increasing maximum displacement levels, eventually leading to multiple transverse cracking in the surface 90° layers as well as formation of delaminations at the interface between the surface 90° layer and neighbouring 0° layer. Density of transverse cracks was quantified and presence of delaminations was qualitatively inspected after each loading-unloading step using optical microscopy. Digital image correlation (DIC) system was used to measure the complete displacement distribution of the laminate in the middle region between the load application points ensuring accurate determination of the laminate mid-plane curvature and the bending stiffness.

The experimental results of bending stiffness reduction and the mid-plane curvature were compared with 3-D FEM calculation results, where a 4-point bending test of a laminate with parametrically variable transverse crack density and delamination length was simulated.

The experimental and numerical results were also compared with analytical model based on Classical Laminate Theory (CLT), where the damaged layer in the laminate is homogenized and replaced by an undamaged layer with effective (reduced) stiffness properties. In the analytical model the effective properties of a damaged layer at any given transverse crack density and delamination length are back-calculated using the in-plane stiffness properties of a representative volume element (RVE) with and without damage. The calculated effective properties of the damaged layer are then used in CLT to predict the reduction of laminate bending stiffness.

The predictions of bending stiffness reduction obtained with the analytical CLT based model yield good agreement with experimental and 3-D FEM results for the tested cross-ply laminate configurations.

1 INTRODUCTION

During the service life laminated composites are subjected to various combinations of thermo-mechanical loads which cause formation of micro-damage in the laminate layers as well as between the layers (delamination). The most typical and earliest damage mode in laminate layers is transverse cracking. For cross-ply laminates the crack plane is transverse to the laminate mid-plane. The crack runs parallel to the fibers in the layer and often (especially in thick layers) covers the whole thickness of the layer and the width of the specimen. On micro-scale these cracks are built by coalescence of multiple fiber/matrix interface debonds. From macroscopic point of view transverse cracking is the

first mode because for unidirectional polymeric composites the transverse tensile strain to failure is lower than other failure strain components.

Due to statistical variation of transverse strength values of the layer, the first transverse crack is created in the weakest position. With increasing applied load (or strain) the number of cracks increases.

The number of cracks per unit length in a layer is an average measure of the extent of transverse cracking called the crack density, denoted as ρ_c . Due to high shear stress concentration and tensile normal out-of-plane stress, local delaminations are often observed at the tip of the transverse crack, where it meets the interface with the next layer. Delaminations are growing during the service life and can be characterized by average delamination length l_d .

An inevitable consequence of micro-damage progression in layers is degradation of macroscopic thermo-mechanical properties of the laminate. Constitutive models for in-plane behaviour of damaged laminates have been historically developed using continuum damage mechanics or micromechanics modelling, see, for example, [1-3]. Most of the analytical solutions are developed for cross-ply laminates with cracks in internal 90° layers only, constrained by a sublaminated layer – a homogeneous orthotropic material with averaged elastic properties representing the sequence of layers on the top and the bottom of the damaged layer. Usually the studied properties are laminate axial modulus, Poisson's ratio and in-plane shear modulus.

Regarding reduction of laminate bending stiffness models based on beam theory in conjunction with shear-lag analysis have been developed in [4, 5].

Despite being a critical property in many applications, the bending stiffness reduction has not been studied to such detail and extent as reduction of normal stiffness and other in-plane properties. Fewer amount of studies related to bending stiffness can be partly associated with a more complex stress-state in bending (non-uniform stress in layers), which in combination with statistical strength distribution sophisticates the damage initiation and evolution analysis. The analysis is furthermore complicated if transverse cracks and delaminations are present in the laminate layers.

Recently, it was shown that methodology based on Classical Laminated Theory (CLT) can be used to predict the laminate bending stiffness reduction due to transverse cracks and delaminations [6]. The analytical model proposed in [6] is based on the concept of effective stiffness of the damaged layer, which can be found using different numerical and analytical models already existing for in-plane loading cases. It was demonstrated in [6] that the bending stiffness results obtained using the CLT based methodology are in a very good agreement with 3-D FEM simulations of a laminate with damage subjected to 4-point bending.

Experimental measurements of the laminate bending stiffness are typically performed using a 3-point or a 4-point bending test set-up [7]. 4-point bending test set-up is recommended compared to a 3-point set-up since the former allows evaluation of the bending stiffness in the region between the load application points and the bending moment and curvature in this region are constant. Presuming that the load and hence the bending moment M_x are accurately measured by the load cell of the mechanical testing machine, for an accurate determination of bending stiffness the experimental measurement of the laminate mid-plane curvature k_x is critical. Displacement transducers can, for example, be used for measuring mid-plane displacements, however, their placement under the bending test rig is often difficult, especially when the samples are small. Furthermore, if the laminate samples are thin, the spring loaded displacement transducers may affect the bending stiffness measurements. From this perspective the use of Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique is very attractive. Apart from being a non-contact measurement technique, the DIC allows measuring the complete distribution of mid-plane displacements and hence an accurate capture of the mid-plane curvature k_x .

The present study is focused on the bending stiffness of cross-ply laminates with damage in surface 90° layers. Carbon fiber/epoxy laminates with different thicknesses of the surface 90° layer were experimentally tested by subjecting to 4-point bending with an increasing maximum applied deflection. As the maximum applied deflection increases in each step, transverse cracks and, at later stages, delaminations form in the laminate reducing its bending stiffness. The mid-plane displacements were measured using DIC 3-D deformation analysis system ARAMIS from GOM mbH. Crack density after each loading-unloading step was quantified using an optical microscope and hence, the relation

between the laminate bending stiffness and the transverse crack density was obtained. The presence of delaminations was qualitatively inspected. The experimental results are compared with 3-D FEM simulations and the applicability of CLT based analytical model proposed in [6] for prediction of bending stiffness reduction is analysed.

2 BENDING STIFFNESS OF LAMINATES WITH DAMAGE

Initially symmetric $[90_n/0_m]_s$ cross-ply laminates subjected to 4-point bending are analysed. A region with constant applied moment M_x exists between loading points leading to constant mid-plane curvature k_x . When transverse cracks are introduced in the surface 90° layers of the laminate, the laminate behaviour in bending becomes unsymmetrical. Cracks in the surface layer, to which the load is applied, are closed due to compressive stresses in this layer whereas cracks in the surface layer under tension are open. The layer with closed cracks behaves like an undamaged layer. Due to the lack of symmetry the B-matrix of the damaged laminate is not zero and some mid-plane strains ε_{x0} , ε_{y0} are also present. When transverse cracking with or without local delaminations evolves, the laminate A, B, D matrices change each in a different way. We analyse the change of the laminate bending resistance with damage development plotting the bending moment to create a unit curvature versus the crack density in a layer, i.e., $M_x/k_x \sim \rho_c$. Other considered damage parameter in addition to crack density is delamination length l_d . The thickness of the damaged ply is denoted as t_{90} .

Boundary conditions are used with applied k_x leading to M_x and $\gamma_{xy0} = k_{xy0} = k_{y0} = 0$. For such case the relevant CLT equations are

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= A_{11}\varepsilon_{x0} + A_{12}\varepsilon_{y0} + B_{11}k_x \\ 0 &= A_{12}\varepsilon_{x0} + A_{22}\varepsilon_{y0} + B_{12}k_x \\ M_x &= B_{11}\varepsilon_{x0} + B_{12}\varepsilon_{y0} + D_{11}k_x \\ M_y &= B_{12}\varepsilon_{x0} + B_{22}\varepsilon_{y0} + D_{12}k_x \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \overline{Q}_{ij}^k t_k, \quad B_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \overline{Q}_{ij}^k \frac{z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2}{2}, \quad D_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \overline{Q}_{ij}^k \frac{z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3}{3} \quad (2)$$

In (2) $t_k, k=1,2,\dots,N$ is the ply thickness; the overline is used to denote the stiffness of the layer in the global system of coordinates. Solving (1) with respect to M_x we can express it in form

$$M_x = C_{11}(\rho_c)k_x \quad (3)$$

where the expression for C_{11} follows from solving (1):

$$C_{11} = \frac{B_{11}(A_{22}B_{11} - A_{12}B_{12}) + B_{12}(A_{11}B_{12} - A_{12}B_{11})}{A_{12}^2 - A_{11}A_{22}} + D_{11} \quad (4)$$

In (4), the elements of the A, B, D matrix are changing with increasing crack density ρ_c . In this study the dependence of bending stiffness C_{11} on crack density and delamination length is investigated. Estimation of the change of laminate A, B, D matrix and hence the change of bending stiffness C_{11} due to transverse cracking and delaminations is described in Section 3.

It has to be emphasized that C_{11} is not equal to bending stiffness element D_{11} , when the laminate has damage.

The boundary conditions in an experimental test could be different than described above, for example, $\gamma_{xy0} = M_{xy} = M_y = 0$, however, the expected differences due to these additional boundary conditions are expected to be small.

3 EFFECTIVE STIFFNESS OF DAMAGED LAYER

In order to use the CLT and expression (4) and study the dependency of bending stiffness C_{11} on transverse crack density ρ_c , the effect of damage has to be first found for a homogenized damaged layer. This was done based on the concept of the effective stiffness [6] and the back-calculation methodology first proposed in [8]. It was shown in [6] that the methodology described in [8], which concerns the effective stiffness in in-plane loading, can also be used for the loading case of bending if the thickness of the damaged layers is sufficiently small.

In this study we analyse a cross-ply laminate with total thickness equal to

$$h = 2t_{90} + 2t_0 \quad (5)$$

Following the methodology described in detail in [6,8], the effective stiffness of a damaged 90° layer can be found as:

$$[\bar{Q}]_{90}^{eff} = [\bar{Q}]_{90} - \frac{h}{2t_{90}} \{ [Q]_0^{LAM} - [Q]^{LAM} \} \quad (6)$$

where the initial stiffness of the 90° layer $[\bar{Q}]_{90}$ and the initial stiffness of the whole laminate $[Q]_0^{LAM}$ are constants that can be found from initial unidirectional (UD) material properties using CLT. It follows that, in order to find the effective stiffness of the damaged layer $[\bar{Q}]_{90}^{eff}$ in (6), it is necessary to find the stiffness of the whole damaged laminate $[Q]^{LAM}$ as a function of crack density ρ_c and delamination length l_d . This can be done, for example, using FEM by modelling representative volume elements (RVE) shown in Fig. 1. The model shown in Fig. 1a is a RVE for a cross-ply laminate with transverse cracks and the model shown in Fig. 1b is a RVE for cross-ply laminate with transverse cracks and delaminations initiating at the tip of the transverse crack and propagating along the 90° and 0° layer interface.

Figure 1: Representative volume elements for case with: a) transverse cracks; b) transverse cracks and delaminations.

In Fig. 1a and 1b parameter l_c characterizes the spacing between the transverse cracks and is directly related to crack density as

$$l_c = 1/2\rho_c \quad (7)$$

The transverse crack spacing l_c and delamination length l_d were parametrically varied in the present work to study the effect of damage on bending stiffness.

In addition, ply-discount model was used in the present study to estimate the asymptotic value of laminate bending stiffness, when the crack density in the 90° layer is high and its effective stiffness drops to zero.

4 3-D FEM MODEL

The effect of damage on bending stiffness was also studied using a 3-D FEM model of a laminate subjected to 4-point bending, schematically shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: 3-D FEM model of a laminate with damage in surface 90° layer subjected to 4-point bending.

A 3-D FEM model schematically shown in Fig. 2 was generated using finite element software ANSYS [9]. The model consists of layers representing the given cross-ply lay-ups $[90_m/0_n]_s$. The total length of the laminate was $L = 150$ mm with the equal distance of 50 mm between the loading points. The width of the laminate beam was $w = 0.8$ mm. The laminate was subjected to 4-point bending loading scheme by applying constant displacement $u_z = -3$ mm on the top surface points. Simple supports were added: the nodes corresponding to coordinates $x = 0, z = 0$ were constrained against displacement in x and z axis directions; the node at coordinate $x = 0, z = 0, y = -0.5 \cdot w$ was additionally constrained against displacement in the y axis direction; the nodes corresponding to coordinates $x = L, z = 0$ were constrained against displacement in the z axis direction and the node corresponding to coordinate $x = L, z = 0, y = -0.5 \cdot w$ was additionally constrained against displacement in y axis direction. Displacement coupling in the y axis direction was applied on the nodes of each edge of the laminate ($y = 0, y = -w$).

The top 90° layer and the 0° layer were modelled without discontinuities (undamaged). In the bottom 90-layer discontinuities in form of transverse cracks were introduced only in the maximum bending moment zone, i.e., in the region between the displacement application points as shown in Fig. 2. The number of transverse cracks was parametrically varied from 0 to 33 uniformly spaced cracks.

Apart from transverse cracks the effect of delaminations at transverse crack tip on laminate bending stiffness was also parametrically investigated. Delamination cracks were introduced between the damaged 90° layer and 0° layer as shown schematically in Fig. 3. Delaminations were assumed to be symmetrical with respect to the transverse crack plane. The delamination length l_d was parametrically varied from 0 to $0.5t_{90}$. The bending stiffness C_{11} was calculated according to definition $C_{11} = M_x / k_x$, where the bending moment M_x was calculated from the reaction forces and the curvature k_x was calculated using mid-plane displacement u_z distribution in the constant bending moment zone (between the load application points), assuming that the deformed shape follows parabolic line.

Because the bending moment M_x in the zone between the load application points is constant, the mid-plane curvature k_x in this region is also constant and can be found as the second derivative of displacements u_z :

$$k_x = -\frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial x^2} \quad (8)$$

Figure 3: Schematic representation of delamination crack with length $2l_d$

Reaction forces and displacement u_z distributions were found in the post-processing stage and derivation according to (8) was performed directly in FEM software ANSYS [9].

5 EXPERIMENTAL TEST

Experimental 4-point bending tests were performed using an Instron 4411 testing machine equipped with 5kN load cell and a DIC 3-D deformation analysis system ARAMIS from GOM mbH. The test rig and the measurement process are shown in Fig. 4. The laminate samples were prepared with one edge finely polished for optical microscopy investigations while the other edge was moderately polished and sprayed with black and white paint to create a suitable pattern for DIC measurements of displacements.

Figure 4: Laminate subjected to a 4-point bending test. Measurements of mid-plane displacements with DIC system ARAMIS.

The laminate samples were subjected to 4-point bending with distance between the loading points equal to 50 mm. The test was run in displacement control with a vertical displacement rate of -2 mm/min. The load measurement data from the Instron 4411 load cell were synchronized with the displacement measurements from the ARAMIS system. Mid-plane displacements were recorded with the ARAMIS system software with the frame rate of 1 – 2 frames per second depending on the length of each test. During the test displacements only in the central region between the load application points was measured. After each experiment a section located exactly on the laminate mid-plane was

created in the ARAMIS software. The section data with the load data and the complete mid-plane displacement u_z distribution were exported to text files. The exported text files were then processed with Matlab software by first fitting the displacement distribution data with 2nd order polynomial function and then performing derivation of the fitting function according to (8). The corresponding bending moment was calculated from the recorded load data. The processed data is the relation between the bending moment M_x and mid-plane curvature k_x . An example of processed experimental data is shown in Fig. 5. The experimental value of bending stiffness C_{11} was obtained as the slope of the linear part of the curve in Fig. 5. For consistency of results, the linear fit to find the bending stiffness from the $M_x - k_x$ data was always performed in a strain region $\varepsilon_x^+ = 0 - 0.4\%$, where ε_x^+ is the tensile strain in the lower face of the laminate.

Figure 5: Experimental data showing relation between bending moment M_x and the mid-plane curvature k_x for a CFEP $[90_2/0]_s$ laminate.

It has to be emphasized that each experimental data point in $M_x - k_x$ curves (see the example in Fig. 5) was obtained by performing polynomial fit for the measured displacement u_z distribution data and derivation according to (8).

6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Carbon fiber/epoxy cross-ply laminates with surface 90° layers with different thicknesses were studied in the present work. Material is denoted as CFEP and the mechanical properties of a UD composite layer are listed in Table 1.

Property	Unit	Value
E_1	[GPa]	104.0
E_2	[GPa]	6.1
ν_{12}	–	0.40
G_{12}	[GPa]	5.0
ν_{23}	–	0.45

Table 1: Elastic properties of unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy (CFEP).

Two different cross-ply lay-ups of CFEP laminate were studied experimentally and by 3-D FEM model: $[90/0]_s$ lay-up with average ply thickness $t_{ply} = 0.60$ mm and $[90_2/0]_s$ laminate with $t_{ply} = 0.62$ mm. In addition, a $[90_2/0_2]_s$ lay-up with ply thickness $t_{ply} = 0.60$ mm was studied using FEM and using the CLT based methodology described in [6, 8].

First, modelling results for $[90_2/0_2]_s$ lay-up are presented in Fig. 6. In Fig. 6a laminate bending stiffness C_{11} as a function of crack density ρ_c is shown. The 3-D FEM results obtained using model shown in Fig. 2 are denoted as “FEM” in Fig. 6 and further in the document. In Fig. 6a 3-D FEM results are compared with results obtained combining CLT expression (4) and the effective stiffness of damaged layer [6, 8], denoted as “E_{eff} FEM”. The notation “E_{eff} FEM” is used because FEM models shown in Fig. 1 were used to calculate $[Q]^{LAM}$ for expression (6). It is demonstrated in Fig. 6a that the combined CLT and effective stiffness approach gives good agreement with direct 3-D FEM calculations and thus can be considered as an accurate approach for prediction of laminate bending stiffness reduction due to transverse cracks. In Fig. 6b the effect of delamination length for $[90_2/0_2]_s$ lay-up is presented. Results in Fig. 6b were obtained using 3-D FEM model shown in Fig. 2 with parametrically varied delamination length (see Fig. 3). As the results in Fig. 6b show, the bending stiffness of laminate C_{11} is further reduced due to increasing delamination length l_d . Also in Fig. 6a and 6b, ply-discount values are presented to indicate the asymptotic bending stiffness, when the crack density in the damaged layer approaches infinity.

Figure 6: Modeling results of bending stiffness C_{11} of a CFEP $[90_2/0_2]_s$ laminate.

Experimental results for $[90/0]_s$ laminate are presented in Fig. 7. Experimental results clearly indicate reduction of bending stiffness C_{11} with increasing crack density ρ_c and the experimental values are in very good agreement with FEM results also presented in Fig. 7. From the optical microscopy observations of the polished edge of the laminate, formation of delaminations was noticed at the interface between the damaged 90° layer and the neighbouring 0° layer. The extent of delaminations l_d was not quantified in the experimental study, however it was found that relatively long delaminations are present at higher crack densities. It can be seen that the experimental data approach the theoretical ply-discount value at higher crack densities. In fact formation of delaminations at high crack densities prevents formation of new transverse cracks and the bending stiffness reduction to ply-discount limit in continuation of loading will be due to growth of delamination length l_d .

Figure 7: Bending stiffness of a CFEP $[90/0]_s$ laminate. Experimental and modeling results.

Experimental results for $[90_2/0]_s$ laminate are shown in Fig. 8. As it can be seen in Fig. 8 the agreement between the experimental results and FEM modeling results is excellent. The experimental data fit very well between the FEM results without delaminations and the FEM results with $l_d = 0.5t_{90}$. Delaminations at high crack densities were noticed in the optical microscopy study of the polished laminate edge, however, their length was not quantified in the present study.

Although in both cases very good, the agreement between experimental and FEM results for $[90_2/0]_s$ laminate (Fig. 8) is better compared to $[90/0]_s$ laminate (Fig. 7), which can be related to generally higher initial bending stiffness and more significant reduction of bending stiffness due to transverse cracking for $[90_2/0]_s$ laminate.

Figure 8: Bending stiffness of a CFEP $[90_2/0]_s$ laminate. Experimental and modeling results.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Experimental measurements of bending stiffness of carbon fiber/epoxy cross-ply laminates were performed. The bending stiffness and its reduction due to transverse cracking and delaminations was measured in a 4-point bending test. The laminate mid-plane displacement distributions were measured using DIC system ARAMIS. From mid-plane distributions the mid-plane curvature was found thus allowing accurate experimental determination of bending stiffness of a damaged laminate.

The experimental results were compared with 3-D FEM results as well as with results obtained combining CLT with effective stiffness approach showing very good agreement between all studied methods. It was shown that experimental results as well as modelling results approach to theoretical ply-discount value, when crack density and delamination length increase.

Performing a 4-point bending test with displacements measured with DIC can be suggested as an accurate method for experimental evaluation of bending stiffness of laminates with damage. The CLT based approach was proved to give accurate analytical predictions of bending stiffness reduction of cross-ply laminates.

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